

Selfless, Sacred Service: A Story of Gratitude

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“Hurry up” it is a hotspot for the virus. 22 March, 2020...All journalistic eyes and television cameras were focused on Pune City. I rushed to the airport as 6E 553 Indigo flight was ready to take off. ‘Please have your seat, Sir’ said the Airhostess. I got perplexed. All had covered their mouths with masks and hands with gloves. That was the fear of Corona that was slowly mounting. Yes, this virus was getting the popularity but not more than Madhya Pradesh political gimmick!!

Flight landed in Calcutta airport and at the entrance I was stopped at a heavy iron gate. A voice said, “Those from Maharashtra and Kerala, please stand in line”. I said to myself, “Thank God, this time I have not been identified with the religion but the state.” With a broad smile, I said, “Excuse me, Ma’am, I’ve arrived from Maharashtra.” To my utter surprise and confusion, she ran away from me crying, “Don’t come near!!”

Quarantine

A nurse came running faster, than an ambulance, and the next moment I had a machine placed on my forehead and my hand was marked ‘QUARANTINE’. Just within a blink of the eye everything happened.

I smiled and entered the quarantine. There were already hundreds inside. I heard a ‘quarantine’ saying, “Where else will we get better meals than this?” He stared at me like a hungry tiger and emptied

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his plate. I understood they are happier to be quarantined than go to the bed hungry.

An hour ago the Lockdown had been announced. It is 26 March 2020, and I happened to read Isaiah 26:20: “Go home, my people and lock your doors hide yourself for a little while until the Lord’s anger has passed”. I said, “Wow Amazing!!”

Schools and offices are closed, malls and markets are empty, events are called off, roads are deserted, flights are grounded, economy is down, and even international boards are closed. People are scared even to look at each other, forget about touching.

I was behind the collapsible gate. After a few days, I heard a voice calling “Mr Saldanha?” I looked around to meet the eyes of a nurse staring at me. I responded “Yes?” “Sir, you need to undergo a blood test in Columbia Asia Hospital. You need to be admitted since you have tested positive for COVID19.” The news was a bombshell!! “I? Positive for...?”

So many nurses came and went. Poking needles, stuffing me with tablets. Tests one after the other and my body was getting shudders.

The New Mother Teresas

Days passed. I saw many nurses and doctors working 24x7. Among them was an old nurse with a radiant face, Alisha by name. Admitted in the city where St. Mother Teresa rests and prays for us, I saw a new Mother Teresa in her!

When she came near me, I appreciated her work. She just replied, “Get well soon”. “Oh. I have found saint in a sinner.” “What?” she exclaimed! “Yes, when I see you in this white dress... Your work and care remind me of St Mother Teresa.”

A moment passed and I felt a drop of water on my hand. It was not too long when I realized that it was her tear, rolled down

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from her cheek. I was confused and apologized for making a statement like that. “Mr Saldanha”, she said, “You must rest now. See you in the morning.”

“Don’t stick to one patient,” was the shout of a matron, almost exploding my ears. She disappeared from my sight. I said to myself, “In this strange situation, I see a finger of God leading me to remember saints.”

The next day I asked her the reason for her tears, because I had lost my sleep the whole night trying to figure out why.

She said, “Nurses are scorned for being late with medicines, even when they are holding their bladder because they don’t have time to use the restroom, even when they are starving because they skip meals, being peed on, puked on, bled on, yelled at... and kept far from their families while taking care of the patients.” She continued, “I am missing my family for the past one month. I am not frightened to get infected so that all of you shed off the virus.”

“Saldanha, Norohona, Aranha and Corona all belong to the same family so corona will not affect my body.” I said jokingly. She smiled.

I switched on my mobile and went to the official site www.covid19india.org. It was shocked to know that cases are exponentially increasing each passing day and people are finding it difficult to get one square meal.

I asked with trembling voice “Why Lord, why this?” I remembered my brother, who taught me an action song ‘*Ghuma, Ghuma ke maara*’. The second line follows ‘*David ne Goliath ko ek pathar se maara*’. I used to have a good laugh. How is it possible to win a war with one stone?!

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Today no more can I laugh. If a virus, which my naked eyes can’t see can kill thousands of people, why not a stone?

The whole night I saw the sky and heard a voice saying “You have been destroying me day after day. In the name of development, you have destroyed my beauty, you have chased and killed all the animals, destroyed fertile lands by mining, polluted the waters and the environment with your toxic gases... Aren’t you satisfied? You wretched human beings! Remember, my death will be your death...” There and then, I resolved, that I should do something for the people and mother earth.

Service with a Smile

The next day doctor told me with a broad smile, “Congrats, you have recovered! Mr. Saldanha and Corona are friends. You are stronger than the Corona!” Once the formalities over, I happily came out of the hospital. But something I missed. Yes, Alisha. I ran back to say ‘Thank you’ to her. My heart came to my mouth... to see her resting on ‘my bed’. She had been tested positive for COVID-19. But no fear or regrets seemed to cross her face. Rather she is happy to say bye. I continued my visit to the hospital.

Today I am sitting and recalling all these incidents in front of her coffin. Jesus sacrificed his life for the humanity. Mother Teresa for the poor and marginalized and Alisha for the Selfless Sacred Service for the Corona patients! That too with a Smile!

Now as this Mother Teresa rests in this wooden box, I can see the same radiance on her face. An angel she is! An angel with white dress! She has fought the fight and won the race.

I said “Thank You Alisha for your Selfless Sacred Service.” *Tick Tick*. I saw my WhatsApp and the message read, ‘Let us see some more humans like Mother Teresa and St Aloysius Gonzaga in our world’. [Please note that this narrative is partly fictional, to protect identity of the characters.- Ed]

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